

LGPD Survey Questionnaire

Informed Consent

I declare that I understood the objectives, risks, and benefits of my participation in the research.

This consent form will be considered signed upon acceptance in the electronic form. However, if participants wish to obtain a printed version, they may request it from the researchers.

I agree to participate

Personal and Professional Profile

1. What is your academic background?

Mark only one oval.

- Computer Science
 - Computer Engineering
 - Information Systems
 - Software Engineering
 - Systems Analysis and Development
 - Information Security
 - Law
 - Business Administration
 - I do not have higher education
 - Other: _____
-

2. What is your level of education?

Mark only one oval.

- High School
- Technical Education
- Undergraduate Degree
- Specialization
- Master's Degree
- Doctorate
- I do not have a degree

3. Do you have any complementary education related to information security or privacy?

Mark all that apply.

- I have participated in a seminar/workshop related to information security or privacy
 - Course in information security or privacy (e.g., Udemy, Coursera, Udacity, Alura, Senac, FGV)
 - Specialization in information security or privacy
 - Master's degree in information security or privacy
 - Doctorate in information security or privacy
 - I do not have complementary education related to information security
-

4. What type of organization do you work for?

Mark only one oval.

- Public Institution
 - Private Institution
 - Mixed Economy Company (composed of public and private capital)
-

5. What position do you currently hold?

Mark only one oval.

- Software Developer / Software Engineer
 - Network Analyst
 - Security Analyst
 - Data Protection Officer (DPO)
 - Project Manager / Project Analyst
 - Lawyer
 - Administrative Position
 - Accounting Professional
 - Human Resources Professional
 - Other: _____
-

6. How long have you held the position indicated in the previous question?

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
 - Between 2 and 5 years
 - Between 6 and 10 years
 - Between 11 and 15 years
 - More than 15 years
-

7. What is the size of the organization where you work?

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 9 employees
 - Between 10 and 49 employees
 - Between 50 and 99 employees
 - More than 100 employees
-

8. In which region(s) of Brazil does your organization operate?

Mark all that apply.

- North
 - Northeast
 - Midwest
 - South
 - Southeast
-

9. What is the main sector of activity of your organization?

Mark only one oval.

- Information Technology
 - Education
 - Telecommunications
 - Financial
 - Legal
 - Oil, Gas and Biofuels
 - Health
 - Transportation
 - Retail
 - Industry
 - Other: _____
-

Considerations on the LGPD

1. How would you define (or classify) your level of knowledge about the LGPD?

Mark only one oval.

- I consider myself an LGPD specialist
 - I have knowledge but do not consider myself a specialist
 - I have superficial knowledge about the LGPD
 - I have only heard about the LGPD
 - I have never heard about the LGPD
-

2. What actions has your organization taken regarding the LGPD?

Mark only one oval per row.

Options per row:

- Yes
- No
- Do not know

Rows:

- Dissemination of information about the LGPD (e.g., email, pamphlet, news, etc.)
 - Distribution of books/tutorials/guides
 - Guidance meetings about the LGPD
 - Lecture/workshop about the LGPD
 - Course about the LGPD
 - Training about the LGPD
 - Action plan, project plan, or similar document
-

3. In your organization, was a committee, working group, or department created to be responsible for LGPD compliance?

- Yes
 - No
 - Do not know
-

4. In your opinion, should there be a committee, working group, or department responsible for LGPD compliance within organizations?

- Yes
 - No
 - Do not know
-

5. In your opinion, which professionals should be involved in LGPD compliance within organizations?

Mark only one oval per row.

Options per row:

- Mandatory
- Preferably
- Not necessarily
- Should not be involved
- Do not know

Rows:

- IT Professionals
 - Lawyers
 - Administrators
 - Accountants
 - Human Resources Professionals
-

6. In your opinion, will there be any organizational/cultural transformation due to the LGPD?

- Yes, I believe it is already happening
- Yes, I believe it should begin soon

- Yes, but I believe it will take time to happen
 - No, no transformation will occur
-

7. In your opinion, to what extent will the LGPD impact your daily professional activities?

- Totally
 - Very much
 - Little
 - It will not impact
 - Do not know
-

8. In your opinion, is LGPD compliance being treated as a priority topic in your organization?

- LGPD compliance is a priority topic
 - LGPD compliance has the same weight as other activities
 - LGPD compliance is not a priority topic
 - Do not know
-

9. In your opinion, will the LGPD increase the privacy and security of Brazilians' data?

- Yes, it will increase privacy and security
 - No, it will not increase privacy and security
 - No, it will decrease privacy and security
 - Do not know
-

10. In your opinion, is the 3-year deadline (August 2018 to August 2021) made available for LGPD compliance feasible?

- Yes
 - No
 - Do not know
-

11. Considering the IT area of your organization, how prepared is it for LGPD compliance?

- Fully prepared
 - Slightly prepared
 - In preparation process
 - Intends to begin preparation
 - Unprepared
 - Do not know
-

12. Are you or have you been part of the committee, working group, or department responsible for LGPD compliance in your organization?

- Yes → Skip to Question 23
 - No
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LGPD Compliance Process Section

(Only for those who answered Yes)

1. How was the committee/group responsible for LGPD implementation created in your organization?

(Open-ended)

2. Which professionals are part of the LGPD implementation committee/group?

Mark all that apply.

- DPO – Data Protection Officer
- Developers
- Database Analysts
- Network Analysts
- Security Analysts
- Quality Analysts
- Project Manager
- Lawyers
- Administrators
- HR Analysts
- Accountants
- Other: _____

3. What stage is the LGPD compliance process currently in within your organization?

- No compliance process initiated
 - LGPD compliance planning phase
 - Initial LGPD compliance processes
 - Advanced LGPD compliance
 - My organization is fully compliant
-

4. Among the LGPD principles listed below, indicate the implementation status in your organization:

Mark only one oval per row.

Options per row:

- Not yet implemented
- Partially implemented
- Successfully implemented
- Not applicable

Rows:

- Purpose
 - Adequacy
 - Necessity
 - Free access
 - Data quality
 - Transparency
 - Security
 - Prevention
 - Non-discrimination
 - Accountability
-

5. Among the LGPD data subject rights listed below, indicate the implementation status in your organization:

Mark only one oval per row.

Options per row:

- Not yet implemented
- Partially implemented
- Successfully implemented
- Not applicable

Rows:

- Confirmation of processing existence
- Access to data
- Correction of incomplete, inaccurate, or outdated data
- Anonymization, blocking, or deletion
- Data portability
- Deletion of personal data processed with consent
- Information about public and private entities with whom data was shared
- Information about the possibility of not providing consent
- Revocation of consent

6. Of the challenges listed below, which were or are being faced in the LGPD compliance process in your organization?

Mark all that apply.

- Lack of organizational knowledge about changes required by the law
- Financial cost
- Three-year deadline
- Bureaucratic barriers
- Lack of support from the government/ANPD
- Scarcity of studies/material/articles
- Cultural change
- Operational change
- Difficulty designating/finding a DPO

- Scarcity of security and privacy specialists
 - Mapping the lifecycle of personal data
 - Translating LGPD into technical operational context
 - Ensuring data subject rights
 - Implementing Privacy by Design
 - Health and economic crisis (COVID-19)
 - None of the above
 - Do not know
-

7. Are there other challenges not listed above? If so, which?

(Open-ended)

8. Of the actions listed below, which were or are being adopted in your organization?

Mark all that apply.

- Creation of a decision-making committee
 - Appointment of a DPO
 - Training for teams
 - Mapping of personal data lifecycle
 - Adoption of new information security regulations
 - Audit and monitoring practices
 - Creation of action plan/project plan
 - Creation/update of Data Protection Policy
 - Creation/update of Incident Response Plan
 - Creation of a Data Protection Impact Report (DPIA)
 - Adaptation of existing systems
 - Procedure for responding to data subject or ANPD requests
 - Secure equipment disposal
 - Contract review
 - Hiring legal advisory services
 - Adoption of methodologies
 - None
 - Do not know
-

9. Are there other actions not listed above? If so, which?

(Open-ended)

10. Of the technologies listed below, which were or are being adopted in your organization?

Mark all that apply.

- Consent Management Platform
 - Data Loss Prevention (DLP)
 - Web Application Firewall (WAF)
 - Database Firewall
 - Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)
 - Physical security controls
 - Secure storage systems
 - Remote work procedures
 - Backup and restoration
 - Removable media protection
 - Monitoring systems
 - Patch/update management
 - None
 - Do not know
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11. Are there other technologies not listed above? If so, which?

(Open-ended)

Final Questions

Would you be available to continue contributing to this research in the future? If yes, please leave contact information.

(Open-ended)

Would you like to make any comment or suggestion about this questionnaire?

(Open-ended)